

Anionic Oxomolybdenum (V) Complexes Containing Triphenyl Phosphonium Cation

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Manuscript received 21 January 1974 ; revised 19 June 1974 ; accepted 26 June 1974.

The isolation of two types of chloro oxomolybdate (V) ions associated with solvent molecules having compositions $(\text{Ph}_3\text{PH})_2\text{MoOCl}_5\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{O}$ and $\text{Ph}_3\text{PHMoOCl}_4(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CO}$ is described. The former loses cyclohexanol on crystallisation from acetonitrile and affords $(\text{Ph}_3\text{PH})_2\text{MoOCl}_5$ and the said clathrate decomposes at a lower temperature when it loses the lattice held solvent (ir evidence) but the uncoordinated acetone molecule in the latter (apparent from ir) is not removable by crystallisation and nor does it escape by heating the complex at a temperature lower than 160° . The compounds have the normal magnetic moments and their ligand field spectra have been interpreted assuming a C_{4v} model.

MOLYBDENUM (V) forms a large number of halo oxomolybdates (V) except with iodine.

The main types are $\text{R}_2[\text{MoOX}_3]$, where $\text{X}=\text{F}, \text{Cl}$ or Br and $\text{R}[\text{MoOX}_4]$, where $\text{X}=\text{Cl}$ or Br and $\text{R}=\text{an alkali metal or ammonium, alkylammonium, pyridinium and quinolinium cation}^{\dagger}$.

The present authors notice that $\text{MoO}_2\text{Cl}_2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in solution in cyclohexanol can be reduced with granulated zinc and hydrogen chloride and the resulting green solution on treatment with triphenyl phosphine affords $(\text{Ph}_3\text{PH})_2\text{MoOCl}_5\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{O}$ which after crystallisation from dry acetonitrile gives $(\text{Ph}_3\text{PH})_2\text{MoOCl}_5$. On conducting the same experiment in acetone medium instead of in cyclohexanol, a compound having the composition $\text{Ph}_3\text{PHMoOCl}_4\text{Me}_2\text{CO}$ separates out. The uncoordinated acetone molecule (cf. ir data) could not be freed from the compound like the cyclohexanol clathrate (ir evidence) even when attempts are made to crystallise the product from acetonitrile. During crystallisation, however, the compound undergoes decomposition liberating a white crystalline product recognised as Ph_3PHCl .

Characterisation and Discussion :

Infrared spectral studies.

As seen in Table 1, a broad band extending on the region $3350\text{-}3500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for the compound $(\text{Ph}_3\text{PH})_2\text{MoOCl}_5\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{O}$ is probably due to the

uncoordinated hydroxo group² of cyclohexanol. This, along with the fact that the compound loses cyclohexanol after crystallisation from acetonitrile, as described earlier, indicates that the cyclohexanol molecule is only held in the lattice (further confirmation by TGA). The $\text{P}-\text{C}(\text{Ph})$ stretch³ of pure triphenyl phosphine at 1092 cm^{-1} shifts to $1104\text{-}1120\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region (Table 1) after coordination with the hydrogen ion in the three phosphonium complexes studied here. The $\text{Mo}=\text{O}$ stretch¹ as a strong absorption at 1000 cm^{-1} in the complex $\text{Ph}_3\text{PHMoOCl}_4\text{Me}_2\text{CO}$ is, no doubt, characteristic of $(\text{MoOCl}_4)^-$ complex whereas the same is obtained at 950 cm^{-1} and 972 cm^{-1} for the cyclohexanol clathrate compound and for the $(\text{MoOCl}_6)^{2-}$ complex, respectively. The $\text{P}-\text{H}$ stretch⁴ is observed as split bands at 2350 (w) and $2400\text{ (sh)}\text{ cm}^{-1}$ regions in the cyclohexanol clathrate compound but this $\text{P}-\text{H}$ stretch is not found in both the $(\text{Ph}_3\text{PH})_2\text{MoOCl}_5$ and $\text{Ph}_3\text{PHMoOCl}_4\text{Me}_2\text{CO}$ complexes. The failure to observe the $\text{P}-\text{H}$ bands in the latter two complexes may be due to a very strong hydrogen bonding with the phosphonium hydrogen of the cation and the oxygen atom or atoms in the anion. In the case of the cyclohexanol clathrate this type of intramolecular hydrogen bonding may not be sufficiently strong to obscure the $\text{P}-\text{H}$ band. In the acetone inclusion compound

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TABLE I—INFRARED SPECTRAL BANDS AND THEIR QUALITATIVE ASSIGNMENTS OF THE MOLYBDENUM (V) COMPLEXES.

Compound and band heads (cm ⁻¹)	Compound and band heads (cm ⁻¹)	Compound and band heads (cm ⁻¹)	Assignments with reference
(Ph ₃ PH) ₂ MoOCl ₅ ·C ₆ H ₁₁ O	(Ph ₃ PH) ₂ MoOCl ₅	Ph ₃ PHMoOCl ₄ Me ₂ CO	
690 (s) 722 (s)	690 (m) 748 (m)	690 (sh) 694 (s)	π (C-H)Ar. ³
748 (s)	724 (s) 754 (sh)	704 (sh) 720(sh)	
—	—	724 (s) 754 (s)	
950 (s)	972 (s)	798 (w) 855 (w)	π (C-H) ³ Aliph.
972 (sh) D	—	1000 (s)	$\bar{\nu}$ (Mo=O) ¹
965 (sh)	—	—	P-H def. ⁴ or cyclohexanol vibrations.
1114 (s)	1120 (s)	1104 (s)	$\bar{\nu}$ [P-C(Ph)] ³
966 (w) 1025 (w)	996 (m) 1026 (m)	1055 (w)	ρ (C-H) ³
1065 (m) 1166 (w)	1080 (s) 1096 (sh)	1130 (w)	
—	1126 (sh) 1156 (s)	1166 (w)	
1480 (m) 1585 (w)	1164 (sh) 1186 (sh)	1194 (w)	
1625 (w) 1640 (w)	—	1350 (m) 1390 (w)	ρ (C-H)Aliph. ³
D	1480 (m) 1590 (w)	1480 (w)	$\bar{\nu}$ (>C=C<) ³
—	1625 (w) 1640 (w)	1585 (w) 1625 (w)	
2350 (w) 2400 (sh)	D	D	$\bar{\nu}$ (>C=O) ³
—	—	1725 (s)	$\bar{\nu}$ (P-H) ⁴
2950 (s)	—	—	$\bar{\nu}$ (C-H)Aliph. ³
3350-3500 (m, b)	3020 (w)	2850 (sh)	$\bar{\nu}$ (C-H)Ar. ³
—	—	3050 (w)	$\bar{\nu}$ (O-H) ³

the C=O band³ occurs at 1725 cm⁻¹ characteristic of free acetone molecule.

The magnetic susceptibility studies :

The magnetic moments of the complexes (Ph₃PH)₂MoOCl₅·C₆H₁₁O (1.80 B.M.), (Ph₃PH)₂MoOCl₅ (1.81 B.M.) and (Ph₃PH)MoOCl₄Me₂CO (1.75 B.M.) closely resemble the spin only value for the 4d¹ species. These values indicate that the spin-orbit coupling interactions in these Mo (V) complexes are very weak owing to the substantial reduction of the values of the coupling constant because of the strong multiple bonding (O → Mo π-bond) between molybdenum and oxygen atoms in the Mo=O oxocation^{6, 7}.

Thermogravimetric analyses.

The cyclohexanol clathrate compound starts to decompose at 60° when probably the cyclohexanol molecule entrapped within the crystal lattice is being lost together with HCl molecules since the horizontal portion of the curve A (Fig. 1) corresponding to the stable intermediate region in the temperature range 190°-260° corresponds to the product Mo₂O₅·4Ph₃P as inferred from the weight loss data and the qualitative analysis of the isolated intermediate compound. But the acetone inclusion compound

Fig. 1. Thermolysis curves of (A) (Ph₃PH)₂MoOCl₅·C₆H₁₁O, (B) (Ph₃PH)₂MoOCl₅ and (C) Ph₃PHMoOCl₄Me₂CO.

starts to decompose at 160° when possibly it loses acetone along with HCl molecules. As infrared data (Table 1) indicates the presence of uncoordinated acetone molecule, this unusual thermal stability may be attributed to the fact that the acetone molecule is very tightly entrapped within the crystal sites due probably to its meeting the exact size requirement. In this case also the formation of an intermediate product in the temperature range 345°-400° (Fig. 1B) is noticed. The weight loss data and the qualitative analysis of the isolated inter-

mediate product suggest it to be $\text{MoOCl}_3\frac{1}{2}\text{P}_2\text{O}_5$. The intermediate products of both the compounds are too hygroscopic to make any thorough characterization. The compound, $(\text{Ph}_3\text{PH})_2\text{MoOCl}_5$; on the other hand, does not give any intermediate product on thermolysis (Fig. 1C).

Molar conductances.

From the molar conductance data of the complexes at different concentrations in dry acetonitrile (Table 2) it is found that in the complexes $(\text{Ph}_3\text{PH})_2$ -

be precipitated out from the dilute solution after generally one or two crops of the green MoOCl_5^{2-} separates out during crystallisation, supporting further the proposed equilibria. The conductance data (Table 2) of the compound $(\text{Ph}_3\text{PH})\text{MoOCl}_4\text{Me}_2\text{CO}$ proposes that the conductance values are far greater than that of 1 : 1 electrolyte⁸ and so, decomposition and subsequent liberation of a mole of HCl per mole of the complex is predicted with which the conductance values tally well. This also explains why the compound could not be crystallised

TABLE 2—CONDUCTANCE-CONCENTRATION DATA OF THE MOLYBDENUM (V) COMPLEXES.

$(\text{Ph}_3\text{PH})_2\text{MoOCl}_5\text{C}_6\text{H}_{11}\text{O}$		$(\text{Ph}_3\text{PH})_2\text{MoOCl}_5$		$\text{Ph}_3\text{PHMoOCl}_4\text{Me}_2\text{CO}$	
Concentration ($\sqrt{C_M} \times 10^3$)	Λ_M ($\text{ohm}^{-1}\text{cm}^2$)	Concentration ($\sqrt{C_M} \times 10^3$)	Λ_M ($\text{ohm}^{-1}\text{cm}^2$)	Concentration ($\sqrt{C_M} \times 10^3$)	Λ_M ($\text{ohm}^{-1}\text{cm}^2$)
3.78	100	3.59	112	3.56	134
2.68	122	2.49	130	2.47	142
1.85	140	1.76	144	1.7	156
1.51	144	1.44	146	1.43	166
1.07	134	1.02	126	1.01	176
0.757	126	0.718	112	0.713	12

$\text{MoOCl}_5\text{C}_6\text{H}_{11}\text{O}$ and $(\text{Ph}_3\text{PH})_2\text{MoOCl}_5$ the Λ_M values in the relatively concentrated solution are close to the values for 1 : 1 electrolytes in this solvent⁸ and the conductance only increases with dilution. For a comparatively dilute solution a Λ_M value close to the value of 2 : 1 electrolyte⁸ is obtained. This indicates that the said compounds behave as weak electrolytes in acetonitrile due probably to the hydrogen bonding interaction between the P—H hydrogen and the oxygen atom present in the anion. One of the important aspects of the conductance studies is that the conductances in both the MoOCl_5^{2-} complexes increase with dilution until a maximum value is reached and thereafter further dilution results in the lowering of the Λ_M values (Table 2). This type of phenomenon has also been observed by us⁹⁻¹² in the cases of some of the dioxouranium (VI), uranium (IV) and dioxomolybdenum (VI) complexes. So, in accordance with our previous proposition here also we propose the following equilibria for the pentachloro complex in acetonitrile :

The triphenyl phosphine and hydrogen chloride are present in 1 : 1 mole ratio and so they are associated to form Ph_3PHCl , which has actually been found to

from acetonitrile when only it suffered decomposition.

These three oxomolybdenum (V) complexes are insoluble in comparatively non-interacting solvents like chloroform, benzene, light petroleum and carbon tetrachloride; moderately soluble in acetonitrile and freely soluble in acetone, ethanol and methanol. Their conductance study has also been made in the last solvent and from the conductance concentration data and the corresponding phoregram (which is similar to the phoregram of HCl in methanol) it appears that each compound dissociates irreversibly in methanol¹³, liberating two moles of HCl per mole of the pentachloro complex and, obviously, one mole of HCl per mole of the tetrachloro complex.

Electronic spectra.

The position and intensity of the electronic absorption bands of the complexes $(\text{Ph}_3\text{PH})_2\text{MoOCl}_5\text{C}_6\text{H}_{11}\text{O}$ and $(\text{Ph}_3\text{PH})_2\text{MoOCl}_5$ are identical. This is quite expected, since both these compounds are supposed to contain discrete MoOCl_5^{2-} species. The spectral data (Table 3) suggest that these are ligand field bands⁹ which can be interpreted assuming a C_{4v} model and also considering a strong asymmetry in Z-axis resulting from the metal oxygen multiple bonding [$\text{O}(2p\pi) \rightarrow \text{Mo}(4d\pi)$]. The band assignments according

to Ballhausen-Gray M.O. scheme¹⁴ are shown in Table 3 wherefrom it appears that the tetrachloro complex, MoOCl_4^- , also contains two ligand field bands attributable to the same types of electronic transitions as suggested in the cases of the pentachloro complexes assuming C_{4v} symmetry. If the tetrachloro complex is discrete and mononuclear

1. Triphenyl phosphonium pentachloro oxomolybdenum (V) cyclohexanolate :

$\text{MoOCl}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1 g) in cyclohexanol (50 ml) was saturated in the cold with dry hydrogen chloride (passed for two hours) in presence of zinc granules and a small amount of zinc dust. To the clear emerald green filtrate was added triphenyl phosphine (2.4 g) in 10 ml of cyclohexanol previously saturated with hydrogen chloride. The resulting solution was

TABLE 3 —ELECTRONIC ABSORPTION BANDS AND THEIR ASSIGNMENTS OF THE ISOLATED OXOMOLYBDENUM (V) COMPLEXES IN ACETONITRILE MEDIUM.

Compound	Band heads cm^{-1}	Molar extinction coefficient (ϵ)	Assignments
$(\text{Ph}_3\text{PH})_2\text{MoOCl}_5 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_{11}\text{O}$	(1) 14,082	5	$2B_g \rightarrow 2E_g$
	(2) 21,930	12	$\rightarrow 2B_g$
$(\text{Ph}_3\text{PH})_2\text{MoOCl}_4$	(1) 14,082	6	$2E_g \rightarrow 2E_g$
	(2) 21,930	14	$2B_g \rightarrow 2B_g$
$\text{Ph}_3\text{PHMoOCl}_4 \cdot \text{Me}_2\text{CO}$	(1) 12,120	4	$2B_g \rightarrow 2E_g$
	(2) 22,478	8	$2B_g \rightarrow 2B_g$

this assumption is quite correct and even if it is a dimer with bridging chloride ligands (which is the only alternative for a dimeric structure with the retention of the normal magnetic moment^{6,7}) it would be capable of existing in cis or a trans configuration and the symmetry of the latter form would not be much lower than C_{4v} . But, as found from the conductance studies, the complex probably decomposes in CH_3CN with the liberation of HCl and so the observed spectrum may be the d-d spectrum of the solvated MoOCl_5 species, as well. At present it is very difficult to resolve this problem

From the profile of the curves as also by actual experiment in very dilute solution of all the three complexes in acetonitrile it appears that the $2B_g \rightarrow 2A_1$ transition as well as the charge transfer bands are all hidden within the low energy tail of the intense absorption of triphenyl phosphine molecule in the UV region.

Experimental :

Triphenyl phosphine was obtained from B.D.H. (England).

The starting material, $\text{MoO}_2 \cdot \text{Cl}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, was synthesized by passing dry HCl over heated (150-200°) dry MoO_3 taken in a pyrex tube¹⁵. The pale yellow sublimable solid was immediately weighed and dissolved in organic solvents in which the complexes are prepared.

concentrated over a boiling water bath when pale green solid separated. These were filtered, washed first with boiling cyclohexanol and then thoroughly with light petroleum and dried in vacuo. Yield 4g., m.p. 170°. Found : C, 55.2 ; H, 4.79, P, 6.80 ; Cl, 19.3 and Mo, 10.4% ; $[(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_3\text{PH}]_2\text{MoOCl}_5 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_{11}\text{O}$ requires, C, 55.1 ; H, 4.81, P, 6.77 ; Cl, 19.4 and Mo, 10.5%.

2. Triphenyl phosphonium pentachloro oxomolybdenum (V) :

$[(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_3\text{PH}]_2\text{MoOCl}_5 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_{11}\text{O}$ (2g) was dissolved in boiling acetonitrile (50 ml) and the resulting solution, after concentration was allowed to cool when green crystals separated. These were filtered off, washed with a very small amount of acetonitrile and then repeatedly with light petroleum and air dried. Yield, 1.6 g., m.p. 275°. Found : C, 52.8 ; H, 3.96 ; P, 7.54 ; Cl, 21.7 and Mo, 11.7% ; $[(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_3\text{PH}]_2\text{MoOCl}_5$ requires C. 53.0 ; H, 3.93 ; P, 7.80 ; Cl, 21.8 and Mo, 11.7%.

3. Triphenyl phosphonium tetrachloro oxomolybdenum (V) acetate :

$\text{MoO}_2 \cdot \text{Cl}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1 g.) in 50 ml of dry acetone was reduced with nascent hydrogen produced by using zinc granules and dry HCl gas as described under 1, and then to the deep brown filtrate was added triphenyl phosphine (1.2 g) in 10 ml acetone previously saturated with dry HCl gas. The light pink crystals were filtered off, washed with a small volume of acetone and then repeatedly with light petroleum and dried in vacuo. Yield 2.4 g., m.p. 200°.

Found : C, 43.8 ; H, 3.80, P, 5.44, Cl, 24.6 and Mo, 16.8% ; $(C_6H_5)_3P\theta MoOCl_4(CH_3)_2CO$ requires, C, 43.8 ; H, 3.83 ; P, 5.39 ; Cl, 24.7 and Mo, 16.7%.

Purification of solvents.

The G. R. (E. Merck) quality methanol and cyclohexanol were distilled before use. Acetonitrile was treated with excess P_2O_5 , kept for two days and then distilled. Acetone (A.R., B.D.H.) was kept mixed with anhydrous K_2CO_3 for 2 days and then distilled. The middle fractions of the solvents so purified were used for preparation of the compounds and their optical absorption and conductance measurements.

Instruments :

Magnetic susceptibilities were measured by the Gouy method using mercury tetrathiocyanato cobaltate as a standard.

Infrared spectra in Nujol mulls were recorded on Perkin Elmer 'Infracord' spectrophotometer equipped with rock-salt optics. The chart papers were calibrated by polystyrene bands at 1603 and 906 cm^{-1} .

Conductances of the solutions were measured in Philips PR 9500 instrument with the help of two stoppered cells—one having a cell factor of 1.50 and the other 1.36. Both the cells gave exactly the same values of molar conductances in each case. All measurements were made at 25° in a well-regulated thermostat with the help of a thermometer capable of recording a change of $\pm 0.1^\circ$.

A Chevenard's Thermobalance of type 3 of ADAMEL of Paris, was used to record the thermolysis curve upto 600°. The rate of heating was 5°/min., on the average.

The electronic spectra were measured in Hilger U.V. spectrophotometer using glass cells in the visible region. In the UV range quartz cells were used.

Acknowledgement

Our grateful thanks are due to Dr. A.K. Majumdar, Senior Professor, Department of Chemistry for his kind suggestions, interest and encouragement.

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